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Title: SOP to evaluate stable ionization spray and calibrate Orbitrap Fusion equipped with EASY-Max Ion source in positive and negative mode.

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IMPORTANT

- Calibrate the MS according to the recommendation status showed in Orbitrap Fusion Tune Application (Tune Window) / Calibration / Status.
- For API housing, **EASY-Max Ion source**, the H-ESI sprayer insert must be equipped with the 'L' needle insert, **HESI LoFlo Needle Insert 50 um ID35G (OPTON-30139)** for calibration.
- Flush the inlet components according to the **SOP to flush the inlet components prior to and after calibration of Orbitrap Fusion**.
- To calibrate the MS, use **Pierce Flex Mix Calibration Solution (A39239)** including calibrants for positive and negative mode. Calibrate the MS in positive mode first.
- Make a note about positive and negative calibration of the MS to Logbook.
- SW: Xcalibur 4.7.69.37, Thermo Scientific SII for Xcalibur 1.8.0.530, Orbitrap Fusion Tune 4.2.4321

Prior to the MS calibration

1. Check there is no flow running to the API housing of MS, if yes:
 - a) set the divert valve to waste (1-6 position) in Tune Application, OR
 - b) turn off the Vanquish Duo LC pumps by Direct Control.

To set up the inlet for direct infusion

1. In Tune window, place the MS to Standby mode.
2. Flush the inlet components, afterwards adjust the 1 and Center position for the H-ESI spray insert.
3. Rinse a clean 500 µL syringe by calibration solution, discard it, then load syringe by 400 µL of calibration solution. Assemble it to the holder and reconnect the syringe's needle with Teflon tubing.

To prepare the MS for calibration

1. In Tune window, place the MS to On Mode.
2. In Tune window panel, click the icons to select parameters:
 - a) **Small molecules** in Application Mode
 - b) + **Positive** or – **Negative** to select ion polarity mode
 - c) **Profile** to collect profile data type
 - d) Σ **OFF** to turn scan averaging off
 - e) \otimes **Valve 1-6** to place the divert valve leading to waste
 - f) **Syringe ON**, then set Flow rate (µL/min): **3** and Volume (µL): **500** and click **Apply**
 - g) In syringe pump setting box, hold **Prime** icon to flush with 100 µL/min
 - h) Check there's no leak of infusion line connections during syringe being in Mode ON and priming

3. To calibrate the MS use:

Pierce Flex Mix Calibration Solution, Open ION SOURCE/Ion Source and DEFINE SCAN, then set values for a respective calibration mode and click **Apply**:

CALIBRATION – Ion Source		CALIBRATION – Define Scan	
Ion Source Type	Heated ESI	Scan Type	MS Scan
Pos/Neg Ion Spray Voltage (V)	3350 / 2400	Detector Type	Ion Trap
Sheath Gas (Arb)	2	Ion Trap Scan Rate	Normal
Aux Gas (Arb)	1.5	Mass Range	Normal
Sweep Gas (Arb)	0	Use Quadrupole Isolation	True
Ion Transfer Tube Temp (°C)	275	Scan Range	150 – 2000
Vaporizer Temp (°C)	40	RF Lens (%)	60
		Normalized AGC Target (%)	100
		Maximum Injection Time (ms)	100
		Microscans	1
		Source Fragmentation	False

To evaluate the spray stability

- By clicking the **Plot Chromatogram** icon, open Plot Chromatogram dialog box and:
 - Click the **Spray Stability** to monitor relative standard deviation (RSD)
 - Select the **TIC** option to plot the full TIC chromatogram and click **OK**
- Review the RSD graph, the signal stability rating and the recommended calibration values:
 - Value of RSD < **15%** for Spray Stability
 - Normalized Level $\approx 0.5 \times 10^5$ of Intensity for Mass Spectrum
 - Injection Time \approx **0.3 sec (as low as possible)**
 - Observe the **characteristic mass spectra profile** for the calibration solution (Figure 1-2)
 - For STATUS pane, check the Spray Current is < 0.5 μ A and < 0.3 μ A for positive and negative mode
- For the RSD above 15%, low signal intensity or long injection time, optimize the ion source parameters:
 - Open panel Optimization from ION SOURCE and click **Pos/Neg Ion Spray Voltage (V)**
 - In Options, set **Start Value**, **Stop Value**, **Step Size** and **Signal Type** as recommended:
For positive mode, set values of 2000 (start), 4000 (stop), 50 (step size) and TIC (signal type).
For negative mode, set values of 1500 (start), 3500 (stop), 50 (step size) and TIC (signal type).
and run by **Optimize** button.
 - Message **“Optimization In Progress”** appears and after tune finishes, accept the optimized value.
 - Optimize nitrogen fluxes for positive and negative mode using recommended values:
For Sheath Gas (Arb), set values of 0 (start), 20 (stop) and 0.2 (step size)
For Aux Gas (Arb), set values of 0 (start), 20 (stop), 0.2 (step size)
For Sweep Gas (Arb), do not optimize tuning values
 - Optionally, assess temperature of the ion transfer tube within 275 - 325°C to reach stable tuning.

To calibrate/check the MS in H-ESI mode

1. In Tune window, open panel CALIBRATION and select Calibration, however, run positive polarity first:
 - a) Mode: Check / Calibrate, if required / Calibrate
 - b) Polarity: Positive / Negative
 - c) Type: Orbitrap Mass / Orbitrap Mass & System
For Orbitrap Mass & System select only: EASY-IC as TrueAfterwards, press Start to run the selected mode
2. Pane Instructions displays notification about the actual state and gives recommendation about the next steps to solve issues. Once the MS calibrated or checked, proceed to Generate Report Now and store PDF to the corresponding folder (year_month_CalRep) in Calibration Reports shortcut. The Pane Status shows passed calibration date with **green notification**.
3. When calibration fails (**red notification**), follow the pane Instructions to solve the related issues and repeat calibration until it passes.

ANNEX

Information about calibration modes:

- Calibrate or check: system runs all the selected mass calibration or check or perform system calibration or check procedures for a selected polarity, including calibration in the correct order.
- Orbitrap Mass: uses masses of a stable Flex Mix spray to calibrate or check the orbitrap masses.
- Orbitrap Mass & System: performs a whole system calibration or check using Flex Mix calibration solution.

Based on the selected calibration type, the following PDF reports are generated:

- Mass_Check_Positive_YYYY-mm-dd_hh-mm_ss
- MassandSystem_Check_Positive_YYYY-mm-dd_hh-mm_ss
- Mass_Calibration_Positive_YYYY-mm-dd_hh-mm_ss
- MassandSystem_Calibration_Positive_YYYY-mm-dd_hh-mm_ss
- Mass_Check_Negative_YYYY-mm-dd_hh-mm_ss
- MassandSystem_Check_Negative_YYYY-mm-dd_hh-mm_ss
- Mass_Calibration_Negative_YYYY-mm-dd_hh-mm_ss
- MassandSystem_Calibration_Negative_YYYY-mm-dd_hh-mm_ss

Figure 1 The characteristic normal-mass range spectrum for **Pierce Flex Mix Calibration Solution** in positive mode

Figure 2 The characteristic normal-mass range spectrum for **Pierce Flex Mix Calibration Solution** in negative mode

Note: The used figures were obtained from Orbitrap Tribrid Series (Thermo Fisher Scientific): Getting Stared Guide and Hardware Manual.